

An overview of non-surgical approaches and their role in Type 2 Diabetes remission

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ABSTRACT:

Diabetes is a major global public health problem. This article is an attempt to provide a short overview of non-surgical approaches that are known to reverse Type 2 Diabetes. A review of existing literature was carried out by using major scientific search database systems. Selected articles from past 6 years were reviewed. Low energy/calorie diet was found to influence in diabetes reversal process. Furthermore, weight loss, counseling and education played an important role in the better glycemic control among samples. The review shares the importance of multipronged approaches in T2D course and prognosis.

Key words: Diabetes reversal, T2D remission, low calorie diet

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a major public health issue worldwide affecting over 100 million people and considered one of the leading causes of death around the globe [1]. Type 2 diabetes (T2D) is known to be associated with increasing age, family history of diabetes, sedentary lifestyle especially leading to overweight and obesity among populations [1]. Family history of diabetes along with obesity could contribute to the problem not only genetically but also due to the fact that families are more likely to share common lifestyle and behaviors [1]. It is evident that it is common to have diabetes among less physically active and obese individuals [1,2]. At micro levels, studies show that subclinical inflammatory reactions leading to higher levels of cytokines could lead to type 2 diabetes [3-5]. A European multicenter population-based cohort study shows that increased levels of C-reactive protein (CRP) and Interleukin-6 (IL-6) increased the risks of T2D among participants [3]. While in the same study, Tumor Necrosis Factor- α (TNF- α) and Interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) along were not predicting diabetes among participants, combined effects of cytokines IL-1 β and IL-6 increased the risks of future diabetes about 3 folds [3]. This is important, because fat cells can act like endocrine tissue and with obesity or increased body fat, there are more fat cells to release inflammatory cytokines hence, leading to increased levels of TNF- α and IL-6 along with other chemicals [4, 5]. This situation could lead to insulin resistance and eventually diabetes [4-6]. Furthermore, glucotoxicity and lipotoxicity due to long term hyperglycemia and elevated fatty acid levels impair β -cell (pancreatic cells responsible for insulin production) function

leading to further deterioration of diabetes [6]. Persistent increased blood sugar levels over the period of time adversely impact on β -cells eventually requiring insulin therapy among 50% of T2D post 10 years of their diagnosis ;hence, early intervention is critical [7].

There is an evidence of T2D reversal post bariatric surgical procedures [4, 5] but the role of non-surgical interventions in remission of T2D is not very clear. T2D remission could be defined as improved insulin sensitivity without any medications where patients are able to maintain their HBA1c levels below 42 mmol/mol and usually accompanied by reasonable weight loss [8].

METHODS AND OBJECTIVES

The present article provides a short overview on the effect of non-surgical approaches in diabetes reversal identified from the findings of existing literature. This literature review was carried out by searching keywords such as diabetes remission, DM reversal, non-surgical intervention in diabetes remission, diet and diabetes etc. on the two prominent scientific search data base systems (PubMed & Google Scholar). The articles from 2011 through 2016 were selected for this paper in aim to share and discuss key findings from the most recently published work in the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A recent UK study from 2016 showed that a sustainable weight loss program supplemented with a very low calorie diet (VLCD) was successful in diabetes remission among 40% of the participants referred as responders (Table 1) [9].

Table 1: Summary of the findings from reviewed studies.

Study/Location/Year	Study Type/Characteristics	Sample/Criteria	Interventions	Outcome
Steven et.al, UK, 2016 [9]	Prospective, Longitudinal, Single-Center	N= 30 Inclusion criteria: T2D duration of 0.5–23 years, Age ≥25–80 years, Body Mass Index 27–45 kg/m ² Exclusion criteria: recent weight loss of >5 kg; treatment with thiazolidinediones, GLP-1 agonists, steroids, or atypical antipsychotics; HbA1c >9.5%; serum creatinine >150 μmol/L; or alcohol intake >3 units/day (women) or >4 units/day (men).	-Discontinuation of all diabetes medicines -VLCD* for 8 weeks (624–700 kcal/day) -Isocaloric intake of normal food for 2 weeks -Weight maintenance program for 6 months	-Weight loss during VLCD 98.0±2.8 kg to 83.8±2.4 kg (P<0.001) -Weight after 6 months 84.7±2.5kg -FBG <7mmol/L= 40% (remission) -FBG <7mmol/L after 6 months=43% (remission)
Mottalib et.al, US, 2015 [10]	Retrospective observational study	N=120 Inclusion criteria: BMI ≥30 mg/kg ² (Obesity) T2D patients who completed one year of follow-up were included in the analysis.	Weight Achievement and Intensive Treatment (WAIT)-12 weeks program -Medication adjustment -Structured modified dietary intervention -Graded, balanced, and individualized exercise intervention -Cognitive behavioral support; adult group education.	-Major improvement with HbA1c <6.5% with or without diabetes medicines=17.3% -Partial remission (HbA1c 5.7-6.5%) without diabetes medicines=2.3% -Complete remission (HbA1c <5.7%) without diabetes medicines=2.3%
Steven et.al, UK, 2013 [11]	Self-reported feedback: emails, letters and telephonic communication between July 2011-September 2012	N=77 Diabetes Reversal Criteria: FBG <6.1 mmol/L and/or HbA1c <43 mmol/mol (6.1%), Diabetes duration 3 months to 28 years.	-General information on diabetes reversal was made available on the website for public and healthcare professionals. E.g. - Reducing portion size (diet)/consuming low energy diet - Sustainable weight loss	-Diabetes reversal among 61% -FBG dropped from 8.3 to 5.5 mmol/L after weight loss (P<0.001) -Weight loss from 96.7±17.5 kg baseline to 81.9±14.8 kg (P<0.001)
Gregg et.al, USA, 2012 [12]	Cohort Study data, Ancillary observational analysis of 4 year randomized controlled trial (baseline visit 08/2001-04/2004, last follow-up 04/2008)	N=4503 Inclusion criteria: BMI >25 mg/kg ² with T2D. Exclusion criteria: HbA1c>11%, blood pressure >160 mm Hg systolic or >100 mm Hg diastolic, or plasma triglyceride levels >600 mg/dL. Reversal Criteria: Partial remission: FBG=100-126 mg/dL, HbA1c= 5.7%-6.5% with no medicines Complete remission: FBG<100 mg/dL, HbA1c <5.7% with no medicines	IL[†] (n=2241) -Include periodic counseling sessions, reduced caloric intake=1200-1800 kcal/d & increasing physical activity 175 min/wk. DSE[‡] (n=2262) 3 group sessions each year focusing on diet, physical activity, & social support. Regulation of diabetes medicines	Weight loss ILI vs. DSE: Net difference at year 1= -7.9% (CI: -8.3 to -7.6) Net difference at year 4= -3.9% (CI, -4.4to -3.5) Remission (partial or complete) with ILI: 1st year:11.5% (P<0.001) at year 4: 7.3% (P<0.001) Remission (partial or complete) with DSE: 1st year:2.0% (P<0.001) at year 4: 2.0% (P<0.001) -Prevalence ratio of complete remission was 6.6 times more common with ILI compared to DSE (P<0.001)
Lim et.al, UK, 2011 [13]	Case control	N=11, matched controls=9 Inclusion criteria: T2D patients (age 35–65 years, HbA1c 6.5–9.0%, diabetes duration <4 years, BMI 25–45 kg/m ²) Exclusion criteria: patients on thiazolidinediones, insulin, steroids or beta-blockers, serum creatinine >150 mmol/l, serum alanine transaminase level >2.5-fold above the upper limit of the reference range, contraindications for MRI.	-VLCD [†] (restricted energy intake) for T2D participants only. -Counselling and support. -8 weeks intervention with a 12 week follow-up.	Baseline to week 8: -HbA1c dropped from 7.4%±0.3 to 6.0%±0.2 (P<0.005) -Plasma glucose from 9.2±0.4 to 5.7±0.5 (P<0.005)

*Very Low Calorie Diet: Liquid diet formula (43% carbohydrate, 34% protein, 19.5% fat) taken as three shakes per day plus up to 240 g of non-starchy vegetables.
[†]IL: Intensive Lifestyle Intervention [‡]DSE: Diabetes support and education intervention
[†]VLCD: liquid diet formula (46.4% carbohydrate, 32.5% protein and 20.1% fat; vitamins, minerals and trace elements); 2.1 MJ/day [510 kcal/day]

It was found that the responders were of younger age and shorter diabetes duration compared with the non-responder group. This indicates that the non-surgical and/or non-pharmaceutical intervention could be more useful in diabetes remission if started earlier in the course of disease. HBA1c levels remained stable throughout the study period among both responder and non-responders. The improvement in blood pressure and cholesterol levels were observed among both groups during maintenance period. The study however had certain limitations such as small sample size and only represents specific ethnic group from the northeastern England.

Mottalib et.al studied the effects of a special 12 weeks program known as Weight Achievement and Intensive Treatment (WAIT) on obese individuals with T2D [10]. The interventions comprised of adjustment of diabetes medications to enhance weight reduction, structured dietary intervention (meal replacements, low carbohydrate, and high protein diet), an exercise program promoting strength training and weekly educational/cognitive support sessions. On 1 year follow-up, 17.3% participants had a major improvement in their glycemic control (with or without medicine) while 2.3% had partial and 2.3% had complete remission without use of anti-hyperglycemic medications (Table 1). It was also found that the remission was more likely to occur among participants who had shorter duration of T2D, were on fewer diabetes medicines and with HBA1c levels <8% at the time of study initiation.

Later on Steven et.al found that the sustained weight loss through low energy diet had a significant impact on the T2D [11]. Exactly 61% of respondents experienced T2D reversal with a significance drop in the body weight and blood sugar levels (Table 1). Similar to the previous two studies [9, 10], the reversal rates were higher among the individuals of shorter duration of disease (T2D duration: < 4 years= 73%, 4–8 years= 56%, > 8 years = 43%). The limitations of this study were that it was not carried out in a group selected through sampling methods or randomization, the respondents self-reported their feedback at their will. We can also assume that the people who didn't participate in the study could be systemically different than who did; hence, the findings cannot be generalized to a larger group of population.

In a 2012 article, the researchers used cohort data from “Look Ahead” (action for health for diabetes) study to observe any impact of intensive lifestyle-based weight loss intervention (ILI) or diabetes support and education intervention (DSE) on partial or complete T2D remission [12]. The individuals who participated in ILI had more weight loss at first and 4th years compared with the ones who were engaged in DSE ($P < 0.001$ for each). ILI participants also experienced statistically significant improvement in their fitness levels at year 1 (15.4%) and year 4 (6.4%) respectively. ILI group was more likely to experience remission compared with DSE. Furthermore, the remission proportions at different years were better among ILI group. Even though the absolute remission was rare, it was found that the shorter duration of T2D, lower baseline HBA1c levels, and large weight loss was associated with better long term remission between years 2-4 (data not shown here).

In an article by Lim et.al, explored the role of negative energy balance (alone) in improvement of β -cell functioning and insulin sensitivity [13]. The intervention group was comprised of 11 T2D patients and a counterpart control group ($N=9$) with no T2D (who didn't receive any intervention). The results were compared with baseline readings and control group. After 1st week of intervention FBG improved from 9.2 ± 0.4 to 5.9 ± 0.4 mmol/l ($p=0.003$) and insulin sensitivity (estimated through the suppression of hepatic glucose output) improved from $43 \pm 4\%$ to $74 \pm 5\%$ ($p= 0.003$) compared to the baseline and controls. By week 8, pancreatic triacylglycerol decreased from $8.0 \pm 1.6\%$ to $6.2 \pm 1.1\%$ ($p=0.03$). There was significant improvement in FBG and HBA1c levels from baseline to week 8 (Table 1). A positive impact was observed on hepatic triacylglycerol ($12.8 \pm 2.4\%$ to $2.9 \pm 0.2\%$, $p=0.003$) and pancreatic triacylglycerol ($8.0 \pm 1.6\%$ to $6.2 \pm 1.1\%$, $p=0.03$) at week 8 and on 12 week follow-up.

The studies are mainly focused on dietary aspects of interventions, followed by educational and counseling support. Physical activity was mostly recorded as a passive intervention except in one reviewed study [12] where 175 minutes per week of exercise was included in the program. We found that dietary modification in terms of caloric restriction had a main role in better glycemic control which was also connected with the sustained weight loss. The low calorie diet seemed to be associated with improvement in underlying

mechanisms associated with T2D. The extent of weight loss was also found to be a critical factor e.g. more the weight loss, better the outcome. Furthermore, another important factor in diabetes reversal was the duration of disease since initial diagnosis i.e. the T2D reversal was higher among the individuals who had a shorter duration of disease. This short review reveals that the larger scale and long term studies on non-surgical and non-pharmaceutical intervention could be useful in further understanding of T2D remission process and mechanism.

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